

TETRAENER

OPTIMAL BALANCING OF DEMAND AND SUPPLY THROUGH RES IN URBAN AREAS

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0. INTRODUCTION

The integration of the principles of sustainable development in land use planning leads to important changes in the practices. New tools of planning are coming out to reach a better balance between environment, economy and society fields. Energy in its various forms and uses (heating, building, mobility, leisure, etc.) are of great importance to our way of life and consuming, and globally to land use planning.

Nowadays, know-how regarding to energy is before all applied to isolated buildings at operational and technical levels. However, reaching a sustainable society involves more than only designing buildings according to low energy requirements and other sustainable criteria. It is the whole urban fabric that has to meet such requirements. It is therefore matter of extending the focus from the building scale to the urban fabric, considering impacts, needs, and resources availability beyond the narrow perimeter of building or even of the district.

Land use planning and energy planning are closely linked since, for instance, road building, infrastructures and facilities settling and development of a given area impact on behaviours and on global energy consumption. Energy is even a mean of developing a given area. Indeed, the existence of heat network or the development of the timber industry for instance may guide the manager in his choices of planning. Energy infrastructures and resources may influence the location of building projects, according to the proximity of resources, and to their architectural design. Consequently, it is fundamental to introduce this new way of thinking about energy at all levels of planning and decision-making, so that energy issues are systematically and formally integrated in land use planning. Objectives of rational and sustainable use of energy force land use planning decreasing energy consumption and dependence on fossils sources. It is however important that such constraints do not hinder the urban development by decoupling environmental impacts from this development. This asks the following questions: what are relevant constraints, at what scale of the land use, and how to implement these constraints?

In this context, the objective is to develop a methodology and associated tools of energy land use and district planning. The methodology aims at providing support for urban development projects from the strategic to the operational levels, so as projects meet the objectives of sustainable and rational use of energy. It is intended to constitute a referential that emphasises for each stage of planning important energy aspects and issues to be taken into account, relevant data and information, involved stakeholders, tools and procedures to be implemented. The main postulate is that energy planning should be integrated in the early stage from the master planning of a given area or project. The objective is to give relevant indications on local energy potentials, and directives on how using these potentials to be then implemented in operational land use plans.

The first part of the report will summarize the practices of energy planning and land use planning in the TetraEner communities (Geneva, San Sebastian and Frankfurt). It will analyse if and how these two ways of planning are integrated, and what are the main lacks. The second part will present the conceptual framework of the methodology than aims at supporting systematic integration of energy and land use planning.

1. SUMMARY OF CURRENT ENERGY AND LAND USE PLANNING PRACTICES IN EACH COMMUNITY

1.1 Objectives

The chapter aims at analysing, in each TetraEner communities, how far energy planning is integrated to land use planning processes. The analysis will consider the practises at different spatial scales (regional and local) and stages of the land use planning process. It will highlight the lacks in terms of introduction of energy issues in urban development procedures, on the basis of which the methodology and tools be will developed in next chapters.

The chapter separately presents energy policies and land use planning practices in each community. Then it analyses how both are integrated. It concludes by formulating guidelines in the perspective of the methodological and tools development.

The three communities of interest belong to countries that can be considered as being federal systems. Policy making of such a system is mainly structured into three levels: federal entity, region, community or municipality. Region is a generic term chosen for the countries of interest: it corresponds to Canton (Switzerland), Autonomous Region (Spain) or Land (Germany). In this chapter, we will focus on the regional and municipal levels.

1.2. Energy policy in each community

Energy policies of Geneva and San Sebastian are directly related to those of their respective region (Canton of Geneva and Basque Autonomous Region). While the city of Frankfurt has developed its own policy.

1.2.1 Geneva

The energy policy of the Canton of Geneva is concretised by the Canton Master Plan of Energy for the period 2001-2005. The driving ideas of the policy are to promote:

- Rational use of the various energy agents;
- Optimal management of energy supply and development of renewable energies;

The Master Plan of Energy is structured into two documents.

The **General Energy Concept**¹ defines the main directives and guidelines of the energy policy for 2010 from the state of 1990:

- To reduce of 10% the consumption in fossil energies and the emission of CO₂;
- To control and stabilise the electricity consumption (no increase from 1990);
- To promote and increase the local production of hydraulic energy;

¹ *Concept Général de l'Énergie 2001-2005*, ScanE, Genève, 2001.

- To increase the share in other renewable energies: +1% for electricity production, +3% for the heating production.

The **Canton Master Plan of Energy**² specifies the guidelines of the General Energy Concept into quantitative objectives. It makes an inventory of the actions to be undertaken in order to meet the objectives. It clarifies the role of the main stakeholders of the Canton: Energy Service of the Canton of Geneva and the Industrial services of Geneva.

Now, the revised process of the plan is coming to the end. The master plan for the period 2005-2009 will come out in January 2008.

1.2.2 San Sebastian

The Basque Country government has developed an energy master plan through a document called "Basque Energy Strategy 2001-2010"³. It expresses orientation towards sustainable energy development based on:

- Intensification of energy efficiency programmes: *energy saving of 15% from 2000*;
- Boost to use of renewable resources: *participation of 15% (4% in 2000)* ;
- Greater participation in cleaner conventional energy sources: *participation of natural gas of 52% (21% in 2000)* ;
- Progressive closure of conventional thermic plants, and substitution by more efficient systems, having less environmental impacts: *1460 MW coming from cogeneration and renewable sources plants (525 MW in 2000)*;
- Devising of an energy policy that contributes to the Kyoto objectives and reduces local environment impacts.

1.2.3 Frankfurt

The city of Frankfurt has an energy master plan that was developed in 2000. This plan is part of the "environmental guidelines" of the city of Frankfurt which was passed by the city council in 2004.

The major political goal of Frankfurt is to reduce CO₂ Emissions 2% every year (which means annual reductions of 180.000 tons of CO₂). To reach this goal, the master plan is now updated with the expertise support of the IFEU Institute (Institute for Energy and Environmental Research) in Heidelberg.

Such a policy is to be linked with the Frankfurt's membership of the Climate Alliance and Energy – Cities: networks of European cities which have committed themselves to reduce CO₂-emissions.

The Energiereferat of Frankfurt is also working on a "climate conservation concept" for Frankfurt with other stakeholders and Frankfurt citizens. The process is called L.E.I.F (Local Energy Initiative Frankfurt) and is part of the European program BELIEF (Building Local Energy Intelligent Forums) that promotes sustainable energy communities.

² *Plan directeur cantonal de l'énergie*, ScanE, Genève, 2003.

³ *Estrategia energética de Euskadi 2010 3E-2010*, Consejera de Industria, Comercio y Turismo, 2001

1.3 Main stakeholders involved in energy policy

1.3.1 Geneva

At the level of the State of Geneva, the energy policy is under the control of the **Energy Service of the Canton of Geneva (ScanE)**⁴ -- a division of the Department of Territory (DT). It has a task to encourage rational use of energy and to promote renewable energy sources from a sustainable development perspective. To this end, the ScanE participates in the development of energy legislation and policy, promotes synergies between business, environmental, consumer and energy policy groups, helps to finance private and public projects with sustainable energy funds, provides its endorsement to construction projects, monitors their progress, and offers assistance to the public as well as to industry experts.

The **Industrial services of Geneva (SIG)**⁵ is a company owned by the Canton of Geneva and its municipalities which provides energy services in the region. This includes:

- Electricity, natural gas, heat, and drinking water production and distribution;
- Rental of telephone network;
- Waste and water management.

1.3.2 San Sebastian

The energy policy is under the control of the **Department of Industry, Commerce and Tourism of the Basque Government**.

Strategies and operational actions are carried out by the **Basque Energy Board (EVE)**⁶ that was created by the Basque Government in 1982 and depends on the Department mentioned above. Its mission is to create the conditions necessary to implement a coherent energy policy, geared towards ensuring availability of energy under the best conditions of supply security, cost and environmental impact, with a view to steering the Basque Country towards a position of sustainable development.

The Basque Energy Board is the main agent of energy policy in the Basque Country. It provides technical assistance in three areas:

- The promotion of energy saving and efficiency measures.
- The strengthening of renewable power resources.
- The development of natural gas.

1.3.3 Frankfurt

At the Land level, **Hessen Energie**⁷ is an Agency founded by the Hessen government and based in Wiesbaden that promotes the environment-friendly use of energy. It provides consulting services

⁴ <http://etat.geneve.ch/dt/site/protection-environnement/energie/master-home.jsp>

⁵ <http://www.sig-ge.ch/>

⁶ <http://www.eve.es/>

⁷ <http://www.hessenenergie.de>

and develops investment projects. Backed by many years of experience with renewable energy and the rational use of energy, the Agency acquired expertise that is systematically implemented in its range of services. The core business of Hessen Energie is to determine the energy-saving potential that could be exploited in state Agencies as well as in small and mid-sized companies by implementing modern technology and intelligent control devices. In this context, power-saving technology, decentralized CHP plants and innovative concepts to optimize building heating play a key role. Another central element is the use of renewable energy sources, such as wind and biomass.

At the community level, the **Energierferat**⁸ has been founded as part of the Cities Environmental department in year 1990. Its aim is to set up and implement the energy and climate protection plan for the City of Frankfurt am Main. The City as founding member of the "Climate Alliance" has set the goal of reducing the CO₂-emissions by 50% until 2010.

The work is concentrated in three working fields:

- office buildings and electricity saving
- energy planning and CHP
- residential buildings and renewable energies

The work of the office is to act as facilitator, organizing round tables between partners, sometimes it sets up feasibility studies as a first step of a project.

The energy services are provided by two companies: **Mainova AG** and **Süwag-Gruppe**.

1.4 Land use planning in each community

1.4.1 Land use planning in general

Generally, in most of occidental countries, and particularly in federal systems, there are three major levels of land use planning⁹ (Rodríguez and Garcia de Diego, 2001):

- Indicative planning: it encompasses sector-based studies and master schemes that diagnose the current situation and express the main lines and directions to which a given area should be planned. It is indicative in the sense it is not legally imposed. It comes into play as a background of any official and legal planning.
- Master planning: it is of strategic, guiding and program-based character. It expresses the general and strategic rule of planning. It is legally imposed to administration bodies.
- Operational or local planning: it expresses the rules of physical urban planning and zone using. It is legally imposed to the owners.

Finally, at the building scale, projects are concretized through an architectural plan.

⁸ <http://www.frankfurt.de/sixcms/detail.php?id=3076>

⁹ Rodríguez A. & Garcia de Diego J., *Síntesis general de los estudios comparados de las legislaciones urbanísticas en algunos países occidentales*, CyTET XXXIII (127), 2001.

The Figure 1.1 summarises the different stages of land use planning and their relation with the spatial level. Every land use plan addresses a given spatial scale and can be classified in one white-box of the tab. The gray-boxes mean that there is no plan possible at these planning and spatial levels. But this can change from a country to another. For instance, in Geneva the master planning also addresses the local level (municipal and district), which is not always the case in other systems where master and zone use planning are not clearly distinct.

	National	Region	Municipality	District	Building
Indicative planning					
Master planning					
Operational planning					
Building project					

Figure 1.1. Stages of land use planning and relation with spatial scales

1.4.2 Geneva

In Geneva, the three first levels of planning are clearly distinct at each scale: Canton (region), municipality and district. We detail here master and local zone use planning levels.

Master planning

On a given territory to be planned, master plans sketch zones where urban, industry, trade developments or other changes in zone using are expected.

The **Master Plan of the Canton of Geneva** (*Plan directeur cantonal*) (passed by the legislative assembly in 2001 and revised in 2006) is made of two documents:

- Concept of Canton land use planning: it defines the general objectives land use planning to the horizon of 2015;
- Canton master scheme: it defines steps and describes the types of projects to achieve the goals and coordinate the various activities having spatial effects.

The **local master plans** determine the main lines of the land use of municipalities or parts of municipal areas (districts). They are compatible with the guidelines of the Canton Master Plan.

Geneva, like others cantons in Switzerland, innovates by planning the land use through a process of two stages: master plan, and then local zone use plan. It gives more importance to the definition of local strategies and enables target more efficient zone use plans on the basis of such strategies. As we will see later, this two stages process enable introduce energy issues earlier in land use planning.

We distinguish to types of local master plans:

- The municipal master plan (*Plan directeur communal*). It is compulsory for municipalities of more than 1000 residents;

- The district master plan (*Plan directeur de quartier*). It determines the main lines of the land use of a district to be developed, situated in one municipality or straddling on several ones. It refines the municipal master plan(s) in the perspective of one or several building projects. Its elaboration is facultative; except for strategic districts (like GLN) defined by the Canton.

Operational planning

The operational plans are carried out at the municipal and district levels.

The municipal land use plan (*Plan d'affectation*) defines at the municipal level the rules of land use. It specifies the built (with indication on density), agriculture, protected, forest, industrial areas.

The *local district plan (Plan localise de quartier)* concretises actions as projected in the upper planning levels. It specifies the conditions to carry out new buildings. It details the volume and the use of each building, accessibility and parking, external works, concessions, etc.

1.4.3 San Sebastian

Like in Switzerland, land use planning in Spain is under the exclusive ability of Autonomous Communities' laws. There is no land use directives at national level.

In Basque Country, the Government defines clearly the use of each property of land and the number of houses that can be built. The main steps of land use planning are:

- Land Use Directives (LUD) (*Plan Regional de la Comunidad Autónoma del País Vasco*): The Basque Government, for the whole country, recommends the uses of the land, taking into account environmental, urban and other issues.
- General Plans (GP) (*Plan General Municipal de Ordenación*): Each Municipality, using the LUD, defines a GP for the land use (industrial, residential, etc.), the boundaries of each use and very generally, the utilizations of each land (number of buildings, dwellings, etc.).
- Development Plans (DP) (*Planeamiento de Desarrollo*): Based on the GP, different parts of the territory are developed through the DPs. Each DP defines in detail the distribution of public and private lands: where the streets are, for each private land the number and type of building. At the block of buildings level, the public lands are developed through urban projects and private lands through architectural projects.

1.4.4 Frankfurt

In Germany, there are four main levels of planning:

- Federal land use planning that expresses the main directives and principles of land use planning in the country (*Raumordnungsgesetz*).
- Land or regional land use planning that expresses the main objectives and principles of land use planning in the Länder or Regions (*Landesentwicklungsplan or Regionalpläne*).
- Municipal land use planning that expresses on the one hand the strategies of urban development that are compulsory for the administration body (master planning); on the other hand, it specifies the type of use in each land of the municipality, which is compulsory for the owners (*Flächennutzungsplan*).

- Operational land use planning that details the urban plans of districts or group of buildings (*Bebauungsplan*).

1.5 Introduction of energy issues in land use planning

This section aims at analyzing how far energy issues are taken into account in each land use plan described above.

1.5.1 Geneva

Masterplan of the Canton of Geneva

One sub-chapter of the masterplan is devoted to the energy management which belongs to the topic of environment preservation and resources management. It presents some general principles and measures of rational energy use in relation with the energy policy of the Canton. The main principle is to diversify the ways of supplying by increasing the use of local and renewable sources of energy: deep geothermy, solar energy and photovoltaic plants, industrial heat discharge reusing, biomass, etc.

The masterplan emphasizes the importance of energy land use planning in order to implement such principles and measures to local land use plans, through energy concepts. It advocates that more information on energy demand and local sources should be made available to urban planners.

However, the masterplan limits itself to state global directives on energy issues and asserts that such directives should be implemented and information collected at local level. In our opinion, the energy aspects could be already reinforced in this early stage, by spatially analysing the distribution of energy demand and local energy sources in the Canton. We would obtain information that does not restrict itself to aggregated and non-spatial indices. Such studies have been made for instance to select optimal sites for grid-connected photovoltaic power plant in a region of Spain¹⁰, or to implement of bioenergy production in Japan¹¹. Spatial analysis of wind energy in Hesse Land was also a way of better introducing this energy source in regional planning (see section 1.5.3). The masterplan could take benefit of similar spatial analysis, not only on specific local energy sources like in the mentioned papers, but analysis that takes into consideration all the types of local sources. The results could be integrated among the other background studies (see indicative planning above) and give indications, in each district of the Canton, on which energy sources to use and with which associated optimal technologies.

Such indications in the masterplan could help to adopt a more global and cross-view between energy topic and other urban and environmental topics. Indeed, maps on local resources and technologies integration can be overlaid and put into prospect with the expected land use developments that have an incidence on energy consumption, for instance:

¹⁰ Carrion J.A. et al., *Environmental decision-support systems for evaluating the carrying capacity of land areas: Optimal site selection for grid-connected photovoltaic power plants*, *Renew Sustain Energy Rev*, article in press, 2007.

¹¹ Ayoub N. et al., *Two levels decision system for efficient planning and implementation of bioenergy production*, *Energy Conversion and Management* (48) 709–723, 2007

- Housing policy: the Canton is planning to build 30'000 housings by 2020. This plan will be achieved by developing existing built areas, increasing the density of detached house areas, building in agricultural areas, etc. All these changes in land use will have impacts on local energy demand. The development in already built areas reduces the urban sprawl phenomenon and consequently the energy consumption. Information on local resources availability may also influence area development plans: for instance the location of a district building may be chosen according to the potential of geothermy in a given area or to the proximity to an existing heating network.
- Industrial areas: the location of new industries may be determined according to the proximity of existing industries (synergetic exchanges), or to the proximity (but not too much) to built areas in order to promote heating networks.
- Shopping centres: the Canton regularly receives requests for the settling of new shopping centres, whereas the available areas are scarce and such settling make lead to conflicts. One criterion in relation with energetic consideration is to reduce the accessibility to cars and to optimise the location on the public transport network.

To sum up, with such integrated views that contribute to plan synergetic exchanges between industries, agricultural and forestry activities (biomass), and urbanisation, the Canton masterplan would reinforce its role in integrating land use policies. This global strategy of land use and energy planning at the Canton level is decisive in order to further undertake operational actions which are coherent from a district to another (local level). For this reason, as we will see thereafter, the lack of background studies on energy opportunities at the Canton level is spread to the local land use plans.

Masterplans of the municipalities

The scale of the municipality is decisive for the land use and energy planning as it is a turning point between the Canton and local scales. Several of recent masterplans include a section devoted to the energy topic. But this section is generally not longer than two pages and expresses general principles and measures. The masterplans are rarely based on background studies that spatially analyse the opportunities of using local energy sources and installations. They often propose to undertake such studies or elaborate energy concepts, but once the masterplan is accepted.

Whereas, we think that, in the same way as for the Canton masterplan, if indications on local energy sources were made available earlier in the process, decision-makers would be able to adopt a global concept of energy supply and efficiency, and to promote renewable sources. This concept would help to develop a more integrated policy of the land use of the municipality and then give very useful directives for the district plans.

Energy concepts in local land use plans

Policy directives

Among the various programmes presented in the Energy masterplan 2001-2005 of the Canton, the programme #9 aims at promoting the integration of energy issues in land use planning through local or district energy concept. The objective of the district energy concept (DEC) is to "give original solutions of production, supply and transfer of energy in order that the district can meet its

needs at least energetic and environmental costs. It results in improving energy efficiency and the use of renewable sources of energy in the perspective of sustainable development¹².

The local energy concept generally takes place in the district masterplan. Each file of masterplan is consulted by all the departments of the State of Geneva, among them, the SCANE that intervenes in order that energy issues are judiciously taken into account. The SCANE gives its notice to the masterplan on the condition that an energy concept is integrated. Thus, since 2002, this department has dealt with more than 10 district energy concepts.

Moreover, through the new Energy masterplan 05-09 to be adopted in 2008, the SCANE wishes to make energy concept more systematic in land use planning, and even legally imposed in a mid-term perspective (until now only the energy concept of important building has a legal force). This reinforced position involves three approaches:

- Systematic: every masterplan document of commune will include a section devoted to energy. Every district masterplan will develop an energy concept.
- Opportunist: a district energy concept will be developed around a project of great scope. It was the case for instance with the Serono building and Geneva Lake Nation concept.
- Priority district: when an existing district shows a great concern, for instance the air pollution with high concentration of NOx. In this case, an energy concept can be carried out to reduce air pollution, by reducing car traffic or forbidding wood heating.

General scheme of district energy concept

Having analysed different practices of DEC in Geneva in the scope of building new districts (Aerni¹²; Conti¹³; Ecotec¹⁴; CSD¹⁵), we propose to resume them through the scheme in Figure 1.2.

The DEC is based on a preliminary draft of a district masterplan. The DEC is part of the Strategic environmental study (SEE) that analyses environmental impacts of the district master plan regarding to various topics, among energy. The results of the DEC are integrated in the SEE report.

¹² Robert Aerni Ingénieur SA, *Etude et stratégie énergétique pour le quartier de La Chapelle-Les-Sciens*, 2004.

¹³ CONTI&Associés Ingénieurs SA, *Stratégie énergétique pour le plan directeur de quartier de Versoix centre*, 2005.

¹⁴ ECOTEC Environnement SA, *Rapport d'évaluation environnementale du projet de plan directeur du quartier de la Gare des Eaux-Vives*, 2006.

¹⁵ CSD Ingénieurs Conseils SA, *Etude énergétique préliminaire des projets PAC MICA & Etoile Annemasse*, 2006.

Figure 1.2. Process of District Energy Concept in Geneva. Abbreviations: SEE (Strategic Environmental Studies, EIS (Environmental Impact Studies), DMP (District Master Plan).

Globally, the process of DEC is made of the following stages.

A. Objectives and issues of the rational use of energy

The report of a DEC generally begins by reminding the main principles and objectives of the rational use of energy:

- To reduce CO2 emissions;
- To improve processes of energy transformation and production;
- To use renewable energy sources as much as possible;
- To promote low and passive energy consumption of buildings;
- To raise public awareness.

B. Analyse of the area of interest, the environmental and energetic context in a restricted and enlarged perimeter

- Existing local land use plans in the area;
- Main energy consumers and producers, opportunity of synergetic exchange with the existing building (district heating);
- Existing installations (gas, electricity, water, district heating network);

- Renewable sources of energy: geothermy, waterway/lake, solar and wind potential, biomass;
- Air pollution: concentration of CO₂, SO₂ and NO_x in the district.

C. Energetic description of the project to be implemented, calculation of energy needs

The preliminary draft of the district masterplan provides the work hypotheses of the future project and the associated data like: floor area, ground area by type of occupation (housing, offices), number of housings, residents and employees, roof area, etc.

All these data enable calculating energy needs for heating/cooling, electricity, hot water according to energetic standards: usual (SIA 380/4) or low-energy standard (Minergie).

D. Definition of supply strategies and alternatives of the project

The strategies and alternatives are devised according to the energy needs (step C) and local energy opportunities (step B). An example of local strategy (district heating system) in the new district of Les Vergers is showed in Figure 1.3. Strategies consider in particular:

- Choice of standard: energetic and exergetic efficiency;
- Sources: renewable (solar, biomass, geothermy), non-renewable (gas, fuel oil);
- Technologies: heat-pump, co-generation, district heating, heat discharge reusing, etc.

E. Comparison of the alternatives and choice of the optimal one

The alternatives are compared according to three groups of criteria:

- Environmental: concerning the greenhouse gas emission, the chosen alternative should contribute to a reduction of 10% in comparison with the emission of 1990;
- Economic: investment costs, exploitation costs (price of kWh/type of energy used), indirect costs (CO₂ taxes, environmental costs);
- Spatial: ground coverage of the installations.

This process is representative of most of masterplan and corresponding DEC, in which it is matter of building a new district. The case of the GLN project is particular, as it takes place in an existing district. In this case, the DEC analyses the opportunities of connecting some existing buildings to the GLN network. For the non-connected buildings, it studies other possibilities of district heating, reduction of consumption (through renovation), using renewable sources of energy (solar in particular).

On the contrary, taking into account energy issues during the elaboration of the district master plan would help take out option on one or other of the following aspects in order to achieve rational use of energy goals:

- choice of location of the buildings according to the proximity to local sources;
- type of use of building (housing, activities);
- density policy;
- location of the district heating boiler;
- orientation of buildings (or other architectural features);
- affectation of flat area for the solar photovoltaic technology;
- parking policy (the reduction of car traffic goes through reduction of number of car parks).

The use of building plots (localisation, density/volume, type of use) is often determined according to the accessibility to a good level of mobility service (in particular in public transportation). We propose thus to enlarge the constraints on building use to other issues that mobility such as energy potentials.

2. In consequence of the previous assertion, the energy concept is elaborated on the basis of advanced hypotheses as regards building location, legal limit of building profile, ground area, etc. The concept takes note of all these characteristics without that the energetic strategies reversely influence the district master plan (except if the nonconformity with objectives of rational use of energy appears to be evident during the notification procedure). The margin for action is thus limited.

In the same way, the margin for action is limited for the energy companies that come into play very late, at the stage of the call for tenders, once the DEC has been finalised by an engineer and accepted by the administration body. It does not prevent, as Zosso¹⁶ points out, that the companies carry out additional studies to verify the solution proposed in the DEC or suggest another alternatives, which leads to additional costs. Yet, the integration between land use and energy planning requires an efficient coordination between public and private partners from the early stages of the process. For this reason, Zosso suggests that the energy companies are involved from the indicative and master planning and express their opinions and ideas on energy issues.

1.5.2 San Sebastian

Land use planning and energy planning are separately carried out without that energy issues are formally taken into account in land use projects at all levels. It does not mean that this integration is inexistent, but it is not institutionally formalised.

Basque Country level

Energy planning for the Country is presented in the Basque Energy Strategy 2001-2010 mentioned above.

¹⁶ Zosso C., *Infrastructures énergétiques et territoire. Analyse des procédures et outils permettant de développer des infrastructures énergétiques à l'échelle du territoire pour le canton de Genève*, Rapport de stage, ScanE, 2007.

In order to concretise the goal of promoting large use of renewable sources, EVE conducted spatial analyses all around the Basque Country: a solar study with solar radiation data in several locations, and wind study with wind speed and direction data in several locations.

Regarding to the integration with land use planning, such studies could influence the Land Use Directives (LUD). But the LUD were developed twenty years ago. So integration will be possible when the LUD will be revised.

Local level

At local level (municipal and district), there are no specific institutional directives that encourage the integration of renewable energy sources and energetic networks in the early stages of planning of a new urban district. Energy planning is provided distinctly from land use plans, only in response of building projects, once they have been already designed. Consequently, energy planning can with difficulty influence building projects.

Figure 1.4. Solution adopted for the production and marketing of energy in the project of Antondegi district. Source: Ente Vasco de la Energía (EVE).

For instance, the Basque Government took the opportunity of two urban development projects to promote efficient energy system such as district heating: Antondegi in San Sebastian (4.030 dwellings) and Bouleta in Bilbao (1.100 dwellings). The Figure 1.4 shows the conceptual scheme of the energy strategy adopted for Antondegi.

For such projects and others (like master plan of energy infrastructures), EVE provides support for devising energetic concepts. They consist in analysing the future energy requirements and the weaknesses of a given energy system, defining the goals of energy efficiency and supply alternatives. Energy concepts are evaluated according to several criteria: reduction of energy consumption, diversification of energy sources, improvement in energetic self-sufficiency, market competitiveness, supply security, etc.

1.5.3 Frankfurt

Energy and land use planning are fairly integrated particularly at local level where some laws make compulsory such an integration.

Regional level (Hesse Land)

In the regional plan for Greater Hesse we find some general directive and suggestions for the use, distribution and production of energy, like:

- Priority for Cogeneration, renewable energy and district heating systems
- Definition of wind energy priority areas – under consideration of average wind velocity, access to the grid, distance to urban areas, etc. This definition is based on the wind analysis that has been done by Government of Greater Hesse and the Germany's National Meteorological Service. Data are available for everyone. In particular, the Hesse Energie Agency together with several communities is running wind-parks (538 plants with 450 MWe).
- Suggestion that communities should set up a local energy concept in order to protect the climate.

Figure 1.5. Geothermal potential (underground temperature) in Hesse Land¹⁷.

Other spatial analyses than wind energy have been made on the availability of local energy sources. For the Greater Hesse, the map in figure 1.5 shows the geothermic potential throughout the Land. Another one shows the solar irradiation so that every planner can calculate the benefits of a Solar thermal or a PV-plant. In the same, at local level, the city of Frankfurt has stored in database the roofs of existing buildings that are favourable for photovoltaic.

Local level

In Frankfurt, numerous district heating systems, that particularly use cogeneration (CHP) technologies have been carried out, or are planned. The map in Figure 1.6 shows the localisation of these systems throughout the city. These networks result from district energy concepts. For instance, two new urban development areas Riedberg (6000 dwellings) and Frankfurter Bogen (2000 dwellings) will implement district heating systems.

The connection of new/existing buildings to new/existing district heating systems is made and legally imposed through urban statuses that are defined in the corresponding areas. Such urban statuses concretise in a way the integration of energy planning (energy concept) in local land use

¹⁷ http://www.hlug.de/medien/geologie/dokumente/erdwaerme/geothermie_web.pdf

planning. For instance, the city of Frankfurt is planning to connect the buildings, that have their own heating system, to an already existing district network. For that, a local urban status is needed.

Figure 1.6. District network systems in Frankfurt. Source: Energierreferat – Frankfurt.

At the building level, the instrument of “City Planning Contracts” with investors is used to define energy standards for new buildings (e.g. passive house standard) which are under national regulations (EnEV) and energy efficient heating supply (that could be cogeneration and/or use of solar thermal plants). The content of these contracts depend on the results of an energy concept for the planning area.

1.6 Conclusion

The sustainable development principle is more and more integrated in urban planning documents, which represents a real progress, since this creates the opportunity of taking into account energy and environmental issues from the beginning of any land use planning project. Moreover, we can notice through the practices of energy planning observed in the various Tetraener communities, that they tend to not restrict themselves to the building scale (as it was the case still recently), but they enlarge the consideration of energy and land use planning issues at the district level or even larger scale.

However, each land use plan, from the region to the district level, is elaborated on the basis of town planning and mobility issues, but very few on those relating to energy. Energy issues are considered in further studies and concepts, once a preliminary draft of a land use masterplan has been carried out. In other words, they are only concretised in the operational decision when a building project is about to be undertaken. As this level, the energy planning is very formalised, it considers legal and technical constraints; information is of technical nature, very precise, but the action margin is limited. On the contrary, at the strategic and wider spatial scale, there is no legal norm, the action margin is higher, but the amount of information is low (Figure 1.7 and 1.8).

	National	Region	Municipality	District	Building
Indicative planning					
Master planning					Fuzzy objectives Aggregated data
Operational planning					
Building project					Accurate objectives Technical data

Figure 1.7. Quality and formalisation of information depending on the planning and spatial scales

In consequence, in the early stages, the integration of energy issues in land use planning is few formalised and depends on the goodwill of the stakeholders (politicians, public services, urban planners, engineers) involved in the process. Due to this fuzziness and the lack of guidelines, the planners have few ideas on which strategy to undertake to develop effective energy solutions.

In short, if energy planning is well developed in the stages of operational planning and building projects, it should be reinforced in indicative and master planning. This latter should systematically include a chapter “energy management” in the same way as it is done for water, environmental, transport or urbanisation management. This chapter should be trans-sector based, explicit the links with the other topics and not restrict to express general principles and guidelines of rationale use of energy. But it has to formalise an intermediate level, between policy directives and the operational level. It should thus coordinate the energy supply on the regional or municipal area at a larger scale than district or building, by taking into account the spatial variability of infrastructures and resources and setting priorities for given zones. This enable add more information in the early stage, guide decision-makers and help them to anticipate the problems that may occur and to target efficient strategies (see dashed curves in Figure 1.8).

Figure 1.8. Evolution of the level of knowledge and action margin during the planning process.

In this perspective, energy concepts will be not only *opportunistic* being carried out in reaction to land use plans or building project. But a *proactive* approach is advocated so that energy planning systematically integrates renewable energy sources in regions and districts, is established before that areas are developed, in the early stages of the projects, at all scales and on the whole urban fabric.

It is for this reason that in next section, we will present a proactive approach that consists in studying local energy opportunities and the feasibility of corresponding technologies before any land use plan, so as to anticipate actions as regards energy planning.

2. METHODOLOGY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL AND ENERGY DISTRICT PLANNING

2.1 Introduction

The objective is to develop a methodology that gives the general framework and specifications for carrying out a process of energy district planning. It aims at proposing guidelines to systematically integrate energy aspects in land use planning, in particular in the master planning stage so as to anticipate actions towards rational use of energy. It does not restrict itself to the district level, but it encompasses the whole process of land use planning, from the regional to local scale, and from the strategic to the operational scale. Indeed, as we have seen in the previous chapter, energy planning at the regional and municipality scales is decisive for local planning.

2.2 Multi-scale approach

We begin our methodological reflection by referring to the multi-scale model developed in section 1.4.1. As shown in the Figure 2.1, the methodology aims at formalising the whole process of energy land planning through top-down and bottom-up approaches. In the top-down process, we systematically identify at stage of land use planning, how energy issues can be introduced and anticipated. The bottom-up process is opportunistic in the sense it formalises how energy issues are integrated in land use planning in reaction to a given urban or building project at local level, and how the project contributes or not to the achievement of rational energy use goals, as defined in the upper levels.

Figure 2.1. Top-down and bottom-up processes in the multi-scale framework.

At each stage of the land use planning, we will bring answers to the following questionings:

- When and how the energy issues come into play and influence land use planning?
- How these issues should influence the district design?
- Which are relevant data and information?
- With which tools and technologies to process information?
- Who are the stakeholders involved in a given stage?

2.3 Conceptual scheme

The following conceptual scheme formalises the whole process of energy land planning.

The process is structured into five major stages. For each stage, we will develop guidelines on how energy issues should be integrated in land use planning and then, how decision-making, information, tools and stakeholders (institutional aspects) should be involved.

The main innovation of the methodology and the associated tools is the definition of energy priority zones at the region level in order to provide a sustainable energy supply. These zones are then progressively refined and detailed at local level. Planners and engineers can thus better take into account energy opportunities and issues in the design of land use plans and energy strategies.

Figure 2.2. Conceptual scheme of the methodology.

2.3.1 Integration of energy issues in land use planning – Deliverables

Through this section we present how the whole system is articulated and works. At each stage, we precise the expected results and deliverables of energy planning, and the way of integrating them in land use planning. We distinguish the two processes: top-down and bottom-up.

Top-down process (systematic)

A. General objectives and principles

>Deliverable of energy planning

Every energy planning should be based on the main energy policies concerning the rational use of energy as stated at international (Kyoto Protocol), national or regional levels. Generally, these principles consider:

- Reduction of CO₂ emission (10 % between 1990 and 2012);
- Reduction of energy needs (energy efficiency, reduction of consumption);
- Supply: increase of the part of renewable sources of energy.

These energy policies will be developed and detailed all along the process going down to the district and building scale. All the actions of energy planning should contribute to achieve these policies.

>Integration with land use planning

Such principles should take part among other topics in the national or regional charters of sustainable land use planning as it is generally the case.

B. Ex-ante diagnosis of energy sources

>Deliverable of energy planning

The objective is to analyse the current situation of a given area in terms of energy availability and demand. The diagnosis delivers two groups of information:

- Energy availability;
 - Existing infrastructures (gas, electricity, water, heating networks, oil tanks, etc.);
 - Opportunities and constraints in using renewable sources (geothermy, biomass, potentials of industrial heat discharges, solar, etc.). Quantification of the potentials;
- Energy demand: current energy consumption of buildings on a given area (housing, activities).

All this information can be displayed as geographical indicators using GIS tools.

>Integration with land use planning

Normally such a diagnosis is carried out in the strategy concept of local project. We suggest already making it from the regional level (Canton, Autonomous region, Land) before any project of master planning. It can be thus integrated into the indicative planning among the studies on other topics (urbanisation, mobility, and environment). Local planning projects can then take benefice of this already-existing information on energy sources and demand in their own diagnoses.

C. Energy priority zones

>Deliverable of energy planning

This deliverable constitutes the main innovation of the proposed methodology. The ex-ante diagnosis is the basis to devise energy strategy on the way of using local energy sources and reducing energy consumption throughout the region.

A given region is split into several zones (they can be urban districts). In each zone, one or more local sources with their corresponding technology can be used for energy supply: heat pumps (air, water surface, underground), solar photovoltaic, biomass, gas, etc. All these alternatives are challenged. The choice of suitable resources and supply technologies should be assessed according to three criteria of rational use of energy¹⁸:

- Energetic and exergetic efficiency of the process of energy transformation;
- Energy and financial cost for the energy supply in given area;
- Impact of the chosen technology on the land use planning (which enable specify the current or future energy requirement).

The land use impact results from the energetic and financial constraints regarding to the two first criteria. It concerns on the one hand the influence radius of the resource which is a function of the distance from the resource and of the land use density (energy requirements); on the other hand the technical and logistical aspects.

This analysis, enable suggest in each zone a limited number of alternatives of synergy between energy sources and associated technologies to be used further in local projects.

>Integration with land use planning

The maps of energy priority zones are included in the region master planning. They strengthen the chapter devoted to the energy policy. Thus, this policy does not limit to general principles and aggregated (non spatial) statistics. In the same way as traditionally a master plan defines areas where some land developments are expected (e.g. densification, change in zone use), the plan adds directives on which energy sources and technologies the land development should use in priority in these same areas.

D. Detailed energy zones at local level (municipality)

>Deliverable of energy planning

In the previous stage, the energy zones are defined according to available data on the whole region of interest. They are consequently based on automatic and systematic information processing. But at local level, in particular the municipality, additional data can be collected on specific and local energy resources. For instance, we can have more detailed information on the potential of using the underground for the geothermy, industrial heat discharges, biomass (waste crops, woods), and the opportunity of connecting some groups of buildings, etc.

On this basis, energy priority zones can be locally refined and split into smaller zones. Local energy zones are then integrated in the global energy strategy of the municipality among energy policies.

>Integration with land use planning

The municipal indicative planning on energy is based on the regional diagnosis and energy priority zones. Combined with additional data on local sources and demand, all this information enables refine energy zones. Such information on energy opportunities made available in the early planning stage results that the master plan of the municipality better takes into account this information and

¹⁸ Gasser D., *Qualification des ressources énergétiques du Canton de Genève. Cas des ressources renouvelables et locales*, rapport d'étude à l'intention du ScanE, 2006.

more globally energy issues. Being integrated in the master plan, the energy strategy can be put into prospect with land use developments.

E. District Energy strategy

At this scale, operational actions are planned and undertaken in a given district.

As we have seen, four types of actions may be considered and lead to a local plan:

- Building of a new district;
- Transformation in an existing district (opportunities of district heating/cooling, renovation, changes in land/building use).
- Priority actions (reducing air pollution).
- Prospecting: analyse of the evolution of the district (in terms renovation and changes in land/(building use) over a long term period (for instance 2030).

>Deliverable of energy planning

The district energy strategy makes reference on the municipal energy strategy (upper level). The process of the elaboration of this strategy does not differ from the one presented in section 1.5.1 for the Geneva context. The difference results in the analyse of local energy opportunities that has been already made in the regional and municipal levels. The engineer has a better idea on the optimal supply technology to use according to the directives made on the local energy zones. He analyses the feasibility of the technological option and its accordance with a given building project.

>Integration with land use planning

As for the municipal level, thanks to stronger integration of energy information and issues coming from the upper levels, the district master and zone use plans is elaborated by better taking into account local energy opportunities. The planner can design the building project in the sense of reducing energy consumption.

Bottom-up process (opportunistic)

The energy and land use planning is not linear but it involves two loop-retroactions that enable going back from lower levels (local) to upper ones (regional).

Loop 1

This loop makes the ex-ante diagnosis dynamic.

Indeed, every new project at local level leads to modify the current situation in two manners:

- Change in energy demand (due to new inhabitants, renovation or change in building/land use);
- Alteration of energy sources. This can be particularly true for limited resources like biomass (woods exploitation) or using underground and surface waters for geothermy (alteration of water temperature).

Consequently, due to these modifications in energy offer and demand, the energy priority zones will be redefined. In other words, in a given zone other resources and technologies may be more suitable in the new situation. This will have impacts on local energy strategies.

Loop 2

For every local project, it is matter of verifying if the project contributes to achieve the global goals of the rational use of energy. In particular, if the project contributes to reduce CO2 emissions and energy consumption, and to increase the supply in renewable energy.

To sum up, the proposed methodology helps urban planners to efficiently and rationally use local energy sources in land use planning and building projects.

2.3.2 Levels of decision making

The energy in land planning mainly involves two levels of decision-making.

Strategic decision

Strategic decision is involved in all levels (regional, municipal and district) of master planning.

Every strategy on land use and energy planning is based on studies and information that are synthesised in the diagnoses.

We distinguish two types of strategic decision according to the scale of planning.

Region

As we have seen, at regional level, energy strategy is concretized trough the definition of energy priority zones that specify which resources and technology to use in the schemes of urban development.

Local

The municipal master planning gives some indications on the areas that can be developed through building projects. But the localisation and density of the projects is not definitive at this level.

Therefore, according to Gasser¹⁹, the objectives of rational energy use influence the strategic decision on two aspects.

The place of land use planning is determined by:

- Buffer zones around the available sources (energy zones). Projects will be developed in priority in zones where renewable energy sources are available and optimal technology can used.
- Objective of rational management of mobility, and particularly, the promotion of collective transportation. Areas will be built in priority around existing collective transport networks.

The density of land use planning that determines the energy needs is influenced by:

- Availability of renewable sources. The municipality may increase the density of a projected district in the zones where the availability of renewable sources is high.
- Mobility. In the same way, the density may be higher in the areas that are connected to the public transport network.

¹⁹ Gasser D., *Utilisation rationnelle de l'énergie sur le territoire. Un enjeu important*, document de cours sur le développement énergétique territorial, 2007.

Operational decision

Operational decision comes into play at the district level, when major options, in particular concerning the localisation of a project and the density, are already taken.

However, it remains a certain amount of action margin concerning three aspects.

a) The feasibility of the energy supply technology as recommended in the plan of energy priority zones is concretely assessed. When various options are proposed, they are compared using Multicriteria analysis. The final choice of supply is thus made at this level.

b) The physical layout of the buildings is determined among others by:

- spaces between building and orientation in order to benefit from solar irradiation;
- heat supply network and boilers.

c) The architecture of the buildings is determined among others by:

- thermal quality of the buildings;
- choice of heating facilities;
- choice of materials (with low grey energy).

2.3.3 Information Tools

The tools used to provide information on energy sources and technical opportunities are shortly summarised in this section. They will be presented in details in other reports.

Database

All the involved tools store their basic data into databases. Data are about energy sources and buildings. And they are all GIS-based, as they process spatial data and display the results on maps.

Energy sources – GIS

We developed a specific GIS tool that stores all the data about the availability of various energy sources at the regional scale. Using spatial analysis tools, it enables quantify the potential of these sources and display them as indicator maps. This GIS – Resource tool will be presented in a further report.

The EPFL, in its deliverable report (WP1.2 Del. 3), presents the development of a platform that includes the following three tools.

ENERGIS

The data of energy consumption of building are often not available. For this reason, the EPFL has developed a simulation model, called ENERGIS, that calculates energy consumption in a district on the basis of statistical analysis. This latter relies on several characteristics of the buildings (age structure, affectation) that are inside a district.

STWP

Any sewage treatment plant (STWP) is a source of water discharge that can be reused by heating pumps. The model calculates if this source can satisfy the energy needs of the district where is situated the plant. It determines how far the rest of the unused part of the source can be used to supply other neighbour districts; at which cost. In other words, the model creates a network of several districts around the plant. The STWP model is one component of the PCoHP model.

PCoHP

This term refers to the coefficient of performance of heating pumps. The CopPAC model challenges for each district of a region the various heating pumps technology according to the availability of local sources (surface waters, geothermy, air, sewage treatment plant), the costs and the energy demands from the buildings (in-temperature). The model analyses the possibility of network or local -based technologies. The technology for a district (zone) is optimal if costs are low and the coefficient of performance is high. The final result is a map of energy priority zones, only for the moment in the point of view of heating pump systems. The next step of the work will be to enlarge the challenging process to other sources and technologies (e.g. biomass, solar).

Simulation (bottom-up loops)

The model ENERGIS can be used to calculate the current energy demand in districts. It can as well simulate the new demand in a district resulting from the construction of a group of new building, change in land use, renovation, or the evolution of buildings and demography towards 2030 for instance.

2.3.4 Data and information

We globally present here the framework analysis and the main types of information involved in the different stages of the process. The data will be then presented in detail together with the corresponding tools.

The data are classified in two groups: data relating to the contextual assessment before any land use project, and those relating to a concrete urban project.

Contextual assessment

The data are classified according to the two major objectives of rational use of energy.

To increase supply in renewable energies

> Natural energy sources

- Underground (geothermy);
- Solar;
- Water surface;
- Wind;
- Biomass (cultivated area, woods, animal manures).

> Existing infrastructure and networks

- Water, gas, electricity;

- Heat networks;
- Industrial heat discharges;
- Synergies.

To reduce energy consumption in land use and buildings

> Existing buildings:

- Age, isolation quality, renovation;
- Number of floors, flats/housing;
- Type of use (affectation);
- Energy needs;
- State of the boilers;
- Roof surfaces (for solar PV purpose).

> Urban fabric

- Spacing, distance between buildings, density;
- Diversity (mix of housings and activities);
- Orientation;
- Land uses.

> Mobility

- Road network;
- Public transport services;
- Car parks;
- Pedestrian and cycles network.

Urban project

The urban project calculates energy needs and consequences (output data) on the basis of the project data given in local master and zone use plans (input data).

Project data (input)

- Surface of the building site;
- Future affectation/use of the buildings;
- Ground coverage (that corresponds to the energetic reference surface);
- Number of flats/housings, inhabitants, employments;
- Roof surface;
- Distance between the building to be connected, distance to a central boiler.

Output data

> Energy needs

- Energy needs for heating/cooling, electricity, hot water according to energetic standards (Minergie, HQE);
- Calculation of heating power (kW);

> Calculation of the effects of the chosen supply strategy

- Environmental: greenhouse gas emission;
- Economic: investment costs, exploitation costs (price of kWh/type of energy used), indirect costs (CO2 taxes, environmental costs);
- Spatial: ground coverage of the installations.

2.3.5 Stakeholders

The involvement of the various stakeholders is decisive for the rational use of energy in land use planning. In this section, we specify for each type of stakeholder what involvement is expected, at which stage of the process. We then formulate recommendations to lead a better coordination between stakeholders.

Figure 2.3. Involvement of stakeholders.

Individual involvement of group of stakeholder

The following stakeholders refer to the general typology proposed by Zosso²⁰.

> Service/Public body

The role of the Public body of a given State, in particular, the energy service, is central in the coordination between all the stakeholders throughout the whole process. It makes sure that every land use plan and building project is in accordance with the energy policy of the State. It systematically introduces energetic concepts in the early stages of local plans (municipality and district). It conditions its acceptance of projects to efficient solutions in term of rational use of energy. In the same way, it imposes such efficiency constraints in the calls for tenders and contracts of concession. It encourages and initiates projects of performance contracting between private or public stakeholders and energy service companies.

> Urban planners

Urban planners like architects are on the land use planning side. They come into play in the elaboration of land use plans both at regional and local levels. They play a major role in integrating objectives of rational use of energy in land use plans. In particular, these plans should take into account local energy opportunities through energy priority zones that are stated in the energy planning side.

> Architects

They play a major role in integrating energy objectives in the operational level of local use plans and building design. They include in their project recommendations coming from local energetic concepts. They should take into account the opportunities of integrating heat networks, local renewable energy sources and they design building with low energy requirements.

> Engineers

Engineers carry out energy planning during almost the whole process. They undertake general studies on energy demand and on the availability of energy sources in a given region (ex-ante diagnosis). They define and calculate energy priority zones at regional and municipal levels to be integrated in master plans. They elaborate energetic concept for local facilities and analyse their technical feasibility.

> Owners

The role of physical or moral owners are important in the end step of the process in the sense that they take the initiative to chose an efficient and rational solution of energy supply, through a performance contracting with an ESCO for instance.

> Energy companies

It was previously suggested that energy companies should be earlier involved in the process from the beginning of any energy district planning. They can be associated while the energy strategies are being devised. The company that shows the most convincing strategies can be already selected for the further project. Moreover, the actual emergence of the ESCO implies that rational energy use is guaranteed through performance contracting projects. The earlier integration of energy issues and information, and the definition of energy priority zones, as proposed in our

²⁰ Zosso C., *Infrastructures énergétiques et territoire. Analyse des procédures et outils permettant de développer des infrastructures énergétiques à l'échelle du territoire pour le canton de Genève*, Rapport de stage, ScanE, 2007.

methodology and tools, would give means and tools to ESCOs to anticipate local energy opportunities and target more efficient solutions.

Coordination

We distinguish three levels of coordination:

- Inside the public body: the integration of energy issues in land use plan involves a better coordination between all concerned public services: those in charge of land use, building, mobility, environment and energy.
- Private public partnership: the public body plays an incentive role towards private partners. It imposes energy objectives to land use projects through energy priority zones and energetic concepts. It advises, informs and trains partners in reaching efficient solutions. It takes advantage of local opportunities to support and encourage private clients to make performance contracting.
- Between private partners: at all levels, there is a need of strong partnership between urban planners and engineers to early integrate energy issues in land use plans. At local and operational level, the partnership mainly involves architects, engineers and ESCOs to integrate in land use plans and building projects opportunities of district heating, using renewable sources and designing building with low energy requirements.

2.4 Application to GLN

In order to illustrate how the methodological process can work, we apply the GLN project to this process. Energy issues were integrated to the district planning around this project, but in a rather intuitive and experimental manner. The application of our methodology enables better formalise how the integration of energy in district planning was carried out in reality (the framework provides a key interpretation of the real process), and how it could have been done better.

The following figure, based on the general framework (in Figure 2.2), illustrates the application:

Figure 2.4. Application of the conceptual scheme to the GLN project

Top-down process

With the methodological proposal, the general context is set from the beginning before any land use project. There is a pre-existing diagnosis, at the regional scale (State of Geneva) on the main infrastructures, energy requirements in building and renewable sources availability. The result of the diagnosis is the definition of energy priority zones that rank the resource use and technologies solutions from the most optimal to the less one. In Geneva, these spatial units of these zones correspond to statistical districts.

Bottom-up process

The GLN project comes into play in this context. It is characterized by two major actions:

- District master plan for the area called “Jardin des Nations”. It consists in planning the district around 6 building projects;
- Among the projects of the plan, the major one is the new building of Serono and the related project of heating and cooling by pumping the water of the lake.

The opportunity of using the lake could have been determined according to the map of energy priority zone that challenge different heat pump technologies (see EPFL report). It effectively shows that in the area (district) where is implemented the master plan project, the solution of using the water of the lake for district heating and cooling is optimal regarding to the coefficient of performance of the corresponding heat pump technology.

Such actions modify the reality and would result in locally updating the diagnosis:

- The new building projects modify the energy requirements in the district.

- The question of the sustainability of the lake resource is asked, as the use of water for cooling leads to locally warm the temperature of the lake (at the discharge point). Environmental impact assessments should then be undertaken (see WP 1.1).
- Finally, the pumping plant and the related network create a new infrastructure in the district.

The next stage is to detail the energy priority zone that corresponds to the district of interest. Globally, it was asserted that using heat pumps with the lake water would be the most optimal solution to supply the district. But this solution can be completed by additional alternatives, above all because not the whole area will be supplied by the GLN network. For this reason, additional information to the current diagnosis should be collected. In the real project, the potential of the existing building roofs were analysed for the solar photovoltaic; drilling were undertaken for the geothermal potential²¹.

Finally, the energetic concept analyses the alternatives of connecting the new building to the GLN, as well as the existing ones. For these latter, the opportunity of connecting depends on the willingness of the owners (clients) to perform a contracting. Complementary alternative solutions were assessed²¹ like the renovation and isolation of the existing building, the change of boiler (supply in wood for instance), the recourse to underground geothermy and solar photovoltaic.

²¹ BG Ingénieurs Conseils, *Plan directeur Energie du quartier de Sécheron-Genève. Phase 1 : analyse du site et de son environnement – données générales locales*, 2001.

3. CONCLUSION

The report has presented a global methodology of energy land use planning that was first based on the analyses of current practises in the TetraEner communities (Geneva, San Sebastian and Frankfurt). These analyses have shown that energy and land use planning are often carried out in parallel. Their integration is still few formalised, in particular in the strategic levels (master planning).

For this reason, the methodology proposes a framework to systematically introduce energy issues in land use planning. It encompasses the whole stages from indicative (diagnosis) to operational planning. It highlights the importance of providing very soon in the planning process a pre-existing analysis before any development of urban project. This analysis includes a diagnosis of energy requirements and resources; and, on this basis, the definition of energy priority zones that results from an optimal synergy between resources, technologies and energy services. The assumption is made that, on the basis of such pre-existing analyses on the energy opportunities, the district energy concepts that come afterwards can target more efficient solutions.

This assumption together with the global methodology should be validated and tested in further applications to district projects in Geneva, San Sebastian and Frankfurt.

For such applications information tools are needed in order to implement the methodology, in particular the stages of diagnosis ex-ante and the definition of energy priority zones. We have already developed GIS tools that diagnoses and calculates the potential of natural energy sources throughout a region. It will be presented in a next report.

The EPFL, in its deliverable report (Del. 3), presents the ENERGIS platform that simulates the energy requirements and calculates energy priority zones for geothermal resources and heat pump systems. The next step will be to extend the definition of such zones for other natural resources (biomass, solar), on the basis of the GIS – Resources.

Finally, the perspective is to integrate all these tools on a common platform, that is a WebGIS interface that provides and displays to stakeholders information on energy sources, building requirements and optimal technologies at different scales: from the region to specific buildings area.

The end result will be a structured good practice methodology and information systems for high performance communities planning to be applied by district planners and other stakeholders.